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THE IMPORTANCE OF THE SOCIAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE FORMATION OF MOTIV IN VISUAL ARTS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the role of the social environment in the formation of fine arts motives in preschool children. The measures signed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to improve the system of preschool education and the creation of conditions for the full intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of preschool children are reflected in the resolutions.

In addition, the author’s research provides a frequency analysis of the answers to the author’s questionnaire of a total of 560 subjects aged 4-7 years of preschool age.

Keywords: *Preschool age, children, fine arts motives, social environment, subject, creativity, creative ability.*

Introduction. On September 30, 2017, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev signed a decree on the establishment of the Ministry of Preschool Education, putting forward the strategy of comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of children in preschool education. In addition, in order to improve the preschool education system, on December 29, 2016, the decision "On measures to further improve the preschool education system in 2017-2021" and on May 9, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the preschool education system until 2030" was adopted. . According to the President’s decision, the features provided for in the second paragraph of the concept of

development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 - "creating conditions for comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of preschool children" constitute the relevance of our topic. It is known that visual art training helps to educate children aesthetically. [1]

In modern psychology, the pre-school age period is classified as the main period. The problem of motive is being studied in world psychology by approaching it from different points of view. Representatives of foreign psychology include K.D. Ushinsky, I.M. Sechenov, I.P. Pavlov, V.M. Bekhterev, A.F. Lazursky, V.N. Myasishev, P.N. Yakobson, V.S. Merlin, L. I. Bojovich, V. I. Selivanov, V. G. Aseev, A. Adler, K. Jung, Horney, Fromm, K. Levin, Z. Freud, E. P. Ilin, Uzbek scientists E. G'. Goziev, G'. B. Shoumarov, V. M. Karimova, B. R. Kadirov, K. A. Ruxieva, A. I. Rasulov determined that the motives that act as the driving force of human behavior are manifested in the structure of the individual.

However, the psychological aspects of the formation of visual art motives in preschool children have not been studied yet.

Analysis of literature on the topic. One of the leading and intensively studied psychological problems today is the problem of talent and creativity. The ideas of purposeful development of a creative personality have been put forward by many scientists of the world. Creative process and psychological aspects of creativity B.G.Ananov, R.Arnhelm, D.B.Bogoyavlensky, M.A.Vollach, J.S.Vygotsky, J.Gilford, V.N.Zruzhinin, N.Kagan, A. Yu. Kazirev, A.N. Leontev, A.N. Luk, A. Maslow, S. Mednik, Ya. A. Panomarev, K. Rogers, I. M. Roseta, S. L. Rubinstein, R. Stenberg, E. P. Torrens, V.S. Covered in the works of Yurkevich and others.

K.D. Ushinsky, N.F. Kapterev, I.A. Sikorsky, A.P. contributed to the development of scientific psychology in Russia. Scientists such as Nechaev, A.F. Lazursky, P.F. Lesgaft made a great contribution. "Subject of human education" by K.D. Ushinsky, "Pedagogical psychology" by N.F. Kapterev, "Child's soul" by I.A. Sikorsky, "Modern experimental psychology and its relation to school education" by A.P. Nachaev, A.F. Lazursky's "Description of a School Student", P.F. Lesgaft's "Child Education in the

Family and Its Importance", K. Elnitsky's "Description of Girls" contributed to the acceleration of psychological scientific research. [2]

In the above-mentioned works, sympathy for different views and disregard for the importance of the social environment are visible. They recognize the social existence of a person and approach it from a scientific and theoretical point of view, but the psychological, physiological and biological aspects and components of a person are not classified, and the external environment is explained as the main factor.

Research methodology. The problem of motive is being studied in world psychology by approaching it from different points of view. In far and near foreign countries, specific psychological schools have emerged, based on which scientific positions and concepts have embodied ideas and directions that differ in essence. Representatives of Russian and ex-Soviet psychology K.D. Ushinsky, I.M. Sechenov, I.P. Pavlov, V.M. Bekhterev, A.F. Lazursky, V.N. Miyasishchev, A.A. Ukhtomsky, D. N. Uznadze, S. L. Rubinshtein, A. N. Leontev, P. M. Yakobson, V. S. Merlin, L. I. Bojovich, V. I. Selivanov, V. G. Aseev and others on this problem who conducted research. [2]

A person's motive circle is reflected in his needs, volitional qualities (acts) and functional capabilities. [7]

In addition to the above considerations, motives perform the function of dynamic management of functional-energetic aspects.

The main types of motivation are extrinsic, intrinsic, internal, external, positive, negative.

1. Motives combined with the social needs of the person, extinguished by the criterion of their essence: ideological motives related to worldview; political motives reflecting the attitude towards domestic and foreign policy, expressing a personal position; moral motives based on moral norms, principles, lifestyle, ethnopsychological characteristics of the society; motives of sophistication (aesthetic) that perceive the needs in relation to the beauty of being.

2. Motives characterized by management and management, which have a common source of emergence, conditioning: comprehensive social motives (Patriotism, self-sacrifice, altruism); group, collective, territorial, universal motives; procedural motives focused on the structure, essence and structure of activity; incentives, reward motives aimed at evaluating the activity product, achieving the goal.

3. Motives reflecting the essence of types of activity: motives embodying social and political realities; motives showing professional training and skills; motives related to study, knowledge (cognitive), creation (creative).

4. Motives that have a common feature of appearance, duration, duration, and stability: constant, continuous, longitudinal motifs; short-term, momentary, instant and second motives; motives that require long-term, time-free, calm behavior.

5. Motives whose emergence and passing rate are measured by bioenergy: strong, powerful, energetic motives within the sphere of influence; medium-speed motifs that appear and pass; weak, empty, weak, unstable motives.

A person's ability is inextricably linked with directly motivated mechanisms, determines their environment and reflects the relationship of dynamic, spiritual influence. The relationship between motive and ability is manifested through activities that are considered the basis of direct performance of mental activity. The implementer of the contents of the motivated system in practice is not limited to determining the activity, but also determines the level of the possibility of the further development of the activity or its mixing with other areas. But the functional possibility of a certain person, activity and the obvious realization of the objective aspects of the same activity, motivation stabilization, development (improvement) also adapt to the objective conditions of the activity. In general, the process of formation, the development of the individual is characterized by the interaction of the activity of the motive, and the activity on the motive. Due to the development of motives, changes occur in the understanding of educational requirements, the re-examination of needs, the expansion of the scope of activities with the help of behavioral rules and criteria, and the relationship of a person with existence. [2; 4]

According to A.N. Leontev, the structure of activity consists of goal-oriented actions and operations. Usually, an activity has its own subject and motive, and if there is a balance (compatibility) between the motive and the subject (body, thing), then it becomes an activity in the original sense. This problem is not new. However, "the reorientation of education from an authoritarian-dogmatic model to a person-oriented model leads to the need to create educational technologies that ensure the realization of the child's personal potential." The primary task of education is to develop the creative potential of a person and create conditions for its realization. [3]

Analysis and results. As experiments are being carried out on the topic of the dissertation, we will highlight our research work based on the results of 560 4-7-year-old children whose total results have been summarized.

A total of 560 subjects took part in the study, of which 326 were 58.2% boys, 234 were 41.8% girls. The age indicators of our test subjects were 4 years 5.9%, 5 years 99 17.7%, 6 years 200 35.7%, 7 years 256 45.7%.

We made a special interview questionnaire with 6 questions for children, and we included the answers to 3 questions in our scientific research work to increase the importance of our research. We also included their answers in the research.

1-To our question, do you like drawing, 552 of our 560 testers, 98.6% answered yes, 8 answered no, 1.4%.

Thus, we did not receive answers to other questions from children who answered no to our 1st question, they were 8, 1.4%. Of the remaining 552 children, 78 (13.9%) were with my father, 148 (26.4%) were with my mother, 38 (6.8%) were with my brother, 63 (11.3%) were with my sister, 13 (2.3%) were with my brother, 16 2.9% with my sister, 133 23.8% with my friend (they gave their friends' names), 27 4.8% alone, 28 5.0% with my kindergarten sister, 8 1.4% with my grandmother have chosen.

We did not receive an answer to this question from 560 of our testers who answered no to question 1 above. 8 of them make up 1.4%. 230 41.1% of our test takers like drawing at home, 305 54.5% of our test takers chose the answer like drawing in

kindergarten, 17 test takers chose the answer everywhere. Our questionnaire originally did not have such an answer option. We just left question 3 blank.

When we asked each of our test subjects who chose the answer option "why", they explained that they have a lot of drawing materials (colored pencils, paper) at home or in kindergarten.

Conclusions and suggestions. In conclusion, we can say that the role of the social environment in the formation of visual art motives in preschool children is very important. 148 of our testers said that they like to draw with their mother. Drawing is a creative process. Artists are formed in the creative process. Today's society needs creative people. This places an additional responsibility on our mothers. It even showed that the role of our women is significant in the development of creativity in society. This places additional responsibility on the mothers of our society. Another large part of our test takers, 133 of them, chose their answers with my friend. We hope that this will serve as a basis for the cooperative formation of science in our society. Only 28 test takers chose the answer "with my kindergarten sister". This indicates the need to change the approach to the preschool education system. [5]

Creation – it is a form of artistic expression and is an important factor in a child's personality development and childhood experience. Having opportunities to develop their imagination and creativity in various forms, children learn to respect the national spiritual heritage and culture. The child learns to express his feelings through music, theater, visual arts, etc. In the field of painting, Raphael Santi's creative ability began to appear at the age of eight, Michelangelo at the age of thirteen, I.E. Repin and V.A. Serov at the age of four, V.I. Surikov at the age of six. Igor Grabar says about himself: "I don't remember at what age I fell in love with painting, but I can't remember a time when I didn't paint." Scientists view creativity as the highest level of human knowledge and transformation of the natural and social world. In the process of creative activity, it is very important to change a person himself (forms and methods of thinking, personal qualities, whether he becomes a creative person). We adults should develop the motivation for creativity in children by creating a psychological environment for

them to engage in visual activities (helping them to feel free, supporting their creative work, helping where necessary). Drawing is a serious and complex work for a child. A certain advantage of drawing compared to other types of activity is that this type of creativity requires the coordinated participation of many mental functions. It helps children to memorize quickly acquired knowledge, to form and correct an increasingly complex idea model of the world. Therefore, according to many psychologists, a child should draw along with speech. Scientist L.S. Vygotsky did not call the picture "graphic speech" for nothing. Children realize themselves and reflect their knowledge of the world through drawing[5; 6]

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